

Endometriosis at the Rectosigmoid Junction, an Unusual Cause of Intestinal Obstruction: A Case Report

López-López Azael¹, Cenicerros-Ulloa Pedro²

¹Department of General Surgery, General Hospital of Gómez Palacio, Durango, México.

²Department of Oncological Surgery, General Hospital of Gómez Palacio, Durango, México.

ABSTRACT

The gastrointestinal tract is the most common site of extrapelvic endometriosis, with the rectum and sigmoid colon being the most frequently affected areas. In the context of intestinal obstruction, the diagnosis remains challenging, as this pathology is usually not considered. We present the case of a patient admitted to the emergency department with an obstructive syndrome secondary to a mass in the rectosigmoid junction, who underwent a low anterior resection. Histopathological examination established the diagnosis of endometriosis.

KEYWORDS: Endometriosis, Colon, Rectum.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
14 November 2025

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com/>

INTRODUCTION

Endometriosis is a chronic gynecological disease characterized by the presence of endometrial-like tissue outside the uterus, affecting approximately 10% of women of reproductive age (1, 2, 3). Outside the pelvis, it primarily affects the rectum and sigmoid colon, occurring in 3% to 37% of cases. Although asymptomatic in many cases, it can rarely cause intestinal obstruction due to infiltration of endometrial tissue (4, 5, 6, 7).

The most common symptoms include abdominal pain, dyschezia (difficulty defecating), cyclical diarrhea and constipation, and in some cases, rectal bleeding, especially when the lesion affects the distal colon (8, 9, 10).

Diagnosis is made through a combination of clinical evaluation, imaging techniques, and surgical procedures, with histopathological confirmation being the gold standard (8, 11). Segmental resection by laparoscopy is the most commonly used treatment for severe cases, improving bowel symptoms and pain (8).

This article will review the clinical case of a patient with intestinal obstruction secondary to rectosigmoid endometriosis, as it remains a rare condition that must be considered when diagnosing the cause of intestinal obstruction in women.

CASE DESCRIPTION

A 40-year-old female patient presented to the inpatient ward with a three-year history of hypothyroidism, social alcohol consumption, and daily vaping.

She was admitted due to a two-month history of recurrent abdominal pain, distension, nausea, vomiting, and difficulty defecating, which had been treated with multiple medications for these symptoms with partial improvement.

She also reported an unintentional weight loss of 9 kg in the last month and blood in her stool on some occasions, which she attributed to her menstrual cycle.

At the time of questioning, she still experienced distension and pain, and had not had a bowel movement in 48 hours despite medical treatment in the emergency department.

Physical examination revealed a distended abdomen, tender to palpation, predominantly in the lower quadrants, and tympanic to percussion. There were no signs of peritoneal irritation. Rectal examination revealed no palpable masses, but there were traces of bleeding.

Laboratory tests were performed, revealing leukocytes of 12.2 cells/mcL, neutrophils of 78%, normal electrolytes and coagulation times, as well as normal blood chemistry.

As part of the study protocol, a non-contrast abdominal CT scan was ordered, which revealed thickening of the rectosigmoid junction. Tumor markers were ordered (Figure 1), and the patient was admitted to the general surgery service

Endometriosis at the Rectosigmoid Junction, an Unusual Cause of Intestinal Obstruction: A Case Report

for conservative management of the intestinal obstruction with suspected tumor at that level.

MARCADOR TUMORAL	VALORES
CA 19.9	20.2 U/mL
CA 125	53.7 U/mL
ALPHA-FETOPROTEIN	1.5 ng/mL
CARCINOEMBRYONIC ANTIGEN	0.5 ng/mL

FIGURE 1. Tumor markers.

An endoscopy consultation was requested to perform a diagnostic colonoscopy. The colonoscopy report showed no lesions on digital rectal examination. The rectum showed erythema with colonic wall edema, narrowing the lumen. The colonoscopy could not be completed due to increased abdominal diameter and generalized tympany. Intestinal perforation was suspected, and the procedure was terminated. An emergency surgical protocol for laparotomy was initiated. During surgery, a perforation in the cecum and a tumor at the rectosigmoid junction were found. Therefore, a right

hemicolectomy was performed due to the cecal perforation, and a low anterior resection was performed due to the tumor's location. A terminal ileostomy was created, the remaining colon was closed proximally, and a distal mucosal fistula was formed.

The histopathological report mentions multiple foci of mural and serous endometriosis associated with fibrosis, surgical margins without lesion, negative for malignant epithelial neoplasia, 21/21 lymph nodes with mixed hyperplasia (Figure 2 and 3).

FIGURE 2. Colon mucosa with preserved architecture. In the submucosa, tortuous and dilated glands are observed, with hemosiderophages present in their lumen.

FIGURE 3. Muscular layer with aggregates of glands with irregular outlines, some dilated, surrounded by cellular stroma compatible with endometrial stroma.

Endometriosis at the Rectosigmoid Junction, an Unusual Cause of Intestinal Obstruction: A Case Report

DISCUSSION

Endometriosis is a chronic inflammatory gynecological disease characterized by the presence of endometrial-like tissue outside the uterus. It affects approximately 10% of women of reproductive age and is a common cause of chronic pelvic pain and infertility (1, 2).

The most commonly affected sites are the ovaries, where endometriomas frequently form. The uterosacral ligaments are also involved, contributing to chronic pelvic pain, as is the ovarian fossa, where dense adhesions are observed. In many cases, the disease affects the pouch of Douglas, causing its obliteration. Outside the pelvis, the rectum and sigmoid colon are the most frequently affected areas of the gastrointestinal tract, while in the urinary tract, the bladder is the most commonly affected site. In cases of deep endometriosis, the abdominal wall and diaphragm may also be involved (3).

Intestinal endometriosis occurs in approximately 3% to 37% of endometriosis cases. The most frequent location is the rectosigmoid colon, which accounts for 70% to 93% of intestinal endometriosis cases. Although intestinal endometriosis is usually asymptomatic, it can cause intestinal obstruction in rare cases, with a reported prevalence of 0.1% to 0.7%. Obstruction can be caused by infiltration of endometrial tissue into the bowel, extrinsic compression, or adhesions (4, 5, 6).

The pathophysiology of this condition is multifactorial. Ectopic endometrial tissue can settle in the pouch of Douglas due to endometrial reflux, and its movement is limited by the sigmoid colon. Once established, the endometrial tissue can invade the intestinal wall, promoting angiogenesis and fibrosis through repeated injury and repair mechanisms. Oxidative stress and the microbiome have also been observed to play a role in its pathogenesis. Deep intestinal endometriosis is associated with neurogenesis and invasion of local nerve fibers, which may contribute to the characteristic abdominal pain (7).

The most common symptoms include abdominal pain, dyschezia, cyclic diarrhea, cyclic constipation, and rectal bleeding. These symptoms can vary depending on the location of the endometriotic lesions in the intestine. For example, rectal bleeding is more common when endometriosis affects the distal colon. In addition, abdominal pain is a frequent symptom and may be associated with cyclic inflammation of the endometrial tissue. Diarrhea during menstruation has also been identified as a prevalent symptom in some cases (8, 9, 10).

The diagnosis of intestinal endometriosis in clinical practice is based on a combination of clinical evaluation, imaging techniques, and, in some cases, endoscopic and surgical procedures. Histopathological confirmation through surgery remains the gold standard for diagnosis. Laparoscopy allows for direct visualization and biopsy of suspicious lesions, providing a definitive diagnosis (8, 11).

Segmental resection is the most commonly used technique for treating intestinal endometriosis, especially when there are

severe symptoms or a risk of obstruction. It is commonly performed laparoscopically and can significantly improve pain and bowel symptoms (8). In our case, the patient presented with clinical signs of obstruction, so a diagnostic colonoscopy was performed. However, due to perforation during the procedure, an exploratory laparotomy was performed to manage the rectosigmoid lesion with a low anterior resection and the cecal perforation with a right hemicolectomy.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this case illustrates the difficulty in arriving at a precise diagnosis of this condition, as it is uncommon and not initially considered. Furthermore, it can mimic other more frequent conditions, making it essential to include it in the differential diagnosis of women of childbearing age.

ABBREVIATIONS: magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), magnetic resonance angiography (MRA), maximum intensity projection (MIP).

REFERENCES

- I. Hameed Bulun SE, Yilmaz BD, Sison C, Miyazaki K, Bernardi L, Liu S, Kohlmeier A, Yin P, Milad M, Wei J. Endometriosis. *Endocr Rev.* 2019 Aug 1;40(4):1048-1079. doi: 10.1210/er.2018-00242. PMID: 30994890; PMCID: PMC6693056.
- II. Adilbayeva A, Kunz J. Pathogenesis of Endometriosis and Endometriosis-Associated Cancers. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2024 Jul 11;25(14):7624. doi: 10.3390/ijms25147624. PMID: 39062866; PMCID: PMC11277188.
- III. Audebert A, Petousis S, Margioulas-Siarkou C, Ravanos K, Prapas N, Prapas Y. Anatomic distribution of endometriosis: A reappraisal based on series of 1101 patients. *Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol.* 2018 Nov;230:36-40. doi: 10.1016/j.ejogrb.2018.09.001. Epub 2018 Sep 5. PMID: 30240947.
- IV. Muşat F, Păduraru DN, Bolocan A, Constantinescu A, Ion D, Andronic O. Endometriosis as an Uncommon Cause of Intestinal Obstruction-A Comprehensive Literature Review. *J Clin Med.* 2023 Oct 6;12(19):6376. doi: 10.3390/jcm12196376. PMID: 37835020; PMCID: PMC10573381.
- V. Sánchez Cifuentes Á, Candel Arenas MF, Albarracín Marín-Blázquez A. Intestinal endometriosis. Our experience. *Rev Esp Enferm Dig.* 2016 Aug;108(8):524-5. doi:10.17235/reed.2016.4292/2016.PMID: 27022815.
- VI. De Ceglie A, Bilardi C, Bianchi S, Picasso M, Di Muzio M, Trimarchi A, Conio M. Acute small bowel obstruction caused by endometriosis: a case

Endometriosis at the Rectosigmoid Junction, an Unusual Cause of Intestinal Obstruction: A Case Report

- report and review of the literature. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2008 Jun 7;14(21):3430-4.
doi: 10.3748/wjg.14.3430. PMID: 18528943; PMCID: PMC2716600.
- VII. Yong PJ, Bedaiwy MA, Alotaibi F, Anglesio MS. Pathogenesis of bowel endometriosis. *Best Pract Res Clin Obstet Gynaecol.* 2021 Mar;71:2-13.
doi: 10.1016/j.bpobgyn.2020.05.009. Epub 2020 Jun 6. PMID: 32646752.
- VIII. Kaufman LC, Smyrk TC, Levy MJ, Enders FT, Oxentenko AS. Symptomatic intestinal endometriosis requiring surgical resection: clinical presentation and preoperative diagnosis. *Am J Gastroenterol.* 2011 Jul;106(7):1325-32.
doi: 10.1038/ajg.2011.66. Epub 2011 Apr 19. PMID: 21502995.
- IX. Lukac S, Schmid M, Pfister K, Janni W, Schäffler H, Dayan D. Extragenital Endometriosis in the Differential Diagnosis of Non- Gynecological Diseases. *Dtsch Arztebl Int.* 2022 May 20;119(20):361-367.
doi:10.3238/arztebl.m2022.0176. PMID: 35477509; PMCID: PMC9472266.
- X. Barchi LC, Callado GY, Machado RB, Chico MA, Damico DC, Lacerda DP, Ricciardi R, Leite RMA. INTESTINAL ENDOMETRIOSIS: OUTCOMES FROM A MULTIDISCIPLINARY SPECIALIZED REFERRAL CENTER. *Arq Bras Cir Dig.* 2024 Jul 1;37:e1806.doi:10.1590/0102-6720202400013e1806. PMID: 38958344; PMCID: PMC11216408.
- XI. Jaramillo-Cardoso A, Shenoy-Bhangle AS, VanBuren WM, Schiappacasse G, Menias CO, Morteale KJ. Imaging of gastrointestinal endometriosis: what the radiologist should know. *Abdom Radiol (NY).* 2020 Jun;45(6):1694-1710.
doi: 10.1007/s00261-020-02459-w. PMID: 32236651.